

Simultaneous estimation of simvastatin and ezetimibe from their combination drug products by RP-HPLC

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Abstract : A simple, precise, accurate and rapid isocratic reversed phase high performance liquid chromatographic method was developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of simvastatin and ezetimibe from their combination drug products. Chromatographic separation was achieved at ambient temperature using μ -Bondapak C₁₈, 3.9 × 300 mm, 10 μ m i.d. column with a simple mobile phase consisted of methanol : water (78 : 22 v/v), delivered at a flow rate of 0.8 mL min⁻¹ and wavelength of detection at 238 nm. The method has shown adequate separation with good resolution in which the retention time of ezetimibe and simvastatin were 4.4 and 8.3 min respectively. The method was found linear over the range of 0.6–60 μ g mL⁻¹ ($r = 0.9999$) for simvastatin and 0.5–50 μ g mL⁻¹ ($r = 0.9999$) for ezetimibe. The intra- and inter-day RSD ($n = 6$) was $\leq 2.0\%$. The developed method was validated according to ICH guidelines and values of accuracy, precision and other statistical analysis were found to be in good accordance with the prescribed values. The proposed method was successfully applied for simultaneous determination of these drugs in combined dosage forms thus enabling the utility of the method for routine analysis.

Keywords : Simvastatin, ezetimibe, reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography, combination products.

Introduction

Simvastatin (SIM) is (+)-{1*S*,3*R*,7*S*,8*S*,8*aR*)-1,2,3,7,8,8*a*-hexahydro-3,7-dimethyl-8-[2-(2*R*,4*R*)-tetrahydro-4-hydroxy-6-oxo-2*H*-pyran-2-yl]-1-naphthyl-2,2-dimethyl butanoate (Fig. 1a). It is a type of medicine called a statin. It works by reducing the production of LDL cholesterol by the liver. The decreased cholesterol production and increased removal of LDL cholesterol from the blood ultimately results in lowered blood cholesterol levels^{1,2}.

Ezetimibe (EZE) is [(3*R*,4*S*)-1-(4-fluorophenyl)-3-[(3*S*)-3-(4-fluorophenyl)-3-hydroxypropyl]-4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-2-azetidinone] (Fig. 1b). It is a type of medicine called a cholesterol absorption inhibitor. It works by preventing cholesterol from being absorbed from the small intestine into the blood stream. These medicines work in different ways, but they have an additive effect on high cholesterol levels. The combination is used to lower high cholesterol in people whose cholesterol has not been lowered sufficiently using a statin alone. Combining the medicines into one tablet aims to simplify treatment for those

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of (a) ezetimibe and (b) simvastatin.

who need to take ezetimibe in combination with a statin to control their cholesterol².

Few methods for simultaneous determination of SIM and EZE from their combination drug products were reported in the literature. Most of these methods were

HPLC methods using different mobile phases such as acetonitrile/phosphate buffer^{3,4} orthophosphoric acid buffer/acetonitrile⁵ ammonium acetate buffer/acetonitrile⁶⁻⁸ and acetonitrile/water/methanol⁹. Other chromatographic methods include an HPTLC method¹⁰ and micellar electrokinetic chromatographic (MEKC) methods^{11,12}. A few UV spectrophotometric procedures were also proposed for the simultaneous estimation of SIM and EZE in dosage forms¹³⁻¹⁷.

Although the combinational use of SIM and EZE is continuously increasing and the simultaneous analysis of these two compounds in their pharmaceutical preparations is not official in British, United States, European and Indian Pharmacopoeias. There is an urgent need to develop and validate analytical methods for the simultaneous analysis of SIM and EZE in their combination dosage forms.

The work included in this paper is therefore focused on developing the optimum chromatographic conditions for the simultaneous estimation of SIM and EZE in their fixed dosage combination.

Experimental

Chemical, reagents and solutions :

Pure samples of EZE and SIM were obtained as gift samples from Saudi Pharmaceutical Industries and Medical Appliances Corporation/Al-Qassim Pharmaceutical Plant (SPIMACO). Commercial tablets (LIPITRIN®) were procured randomly from Egyptian market in several different strength combination including 10 : 10, 10 : 20 and 10 : 40 mg (EZE/SIM) manufactured by Chemipharm Pharmaceutical Industries (Egypt). Methanol was of HPLC grade and purchased from Panreac Qimica, Barcelona-Espania and used without further purification. HPLC grade deionized water was used throughout this work. Primary stock solution of SIM (100 µg/mL) and EZE (100 µg/mL) were prepared separately in methanol. These solutions were stable for at least three weeks if kept in refrigerator. The stock solutions were further diluted with a mixture of methanol and water in ratio 50 : 50 (v/v) to obtain the working standard solutions in the concentration range of 0.5–50 µg/mL for EZE and 0.6– 60 µg/mL

for SIM. The working standard solutions of both drugs were prepared individually and filtered through 0.45 µm filter. Twenty microliters of each solution was injected each time into the column at a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min. The detection of the method was monitored at 238 nm. Each of these solutions was injected for three times into the column and the corresponding chromatograms were obtained. Graphs were plotted between the mean peak areas of the drug with respect to concentration. Regression equations were calculated.

Analysis of synthetic mixtures :

Aliquots of the stock solutions of EZE and SIM were further diluted with a mixture of methanol and water 50 : 50 (v/v) to yield different concentration ratios (1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 4 and 1 : 8 w/w). Triplicate injections of each solution were performed. The concentration of each drug was obtained using the calibration curves or the corresponding regression equations.

Sample preparations :

Tablets : Seven tablets were weighed, powdered and an amount of the powder equivalent to a suitable amount of drug (according to the label claim) was weighed and transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask containing 25 mL of methanol. The flask with its content was sonicated for 15 min and made up to volume with a mixture of methanol and water (50 : 50 v/v). Then the above solution was filtered. Appropriate dilutions of this solution were made with the mixture of (50 : 50 v/v) methanol/water to obtain concentrations in calibration range for both drugs. These solutions were filtered through 0.45 µm filter and then injected for LC analysis. The concentration of each sample was obtained using the calibration curve or the corresponding regression equation.

Chromatography : Chromatographic separation was performed on a Young Lin instrument (ACME 9000) equipped with 3 modules gradient pump, a variable UV wavelength detector (set at 238 nm) and degasser. Samples were injected with a Rheodyne manual injector with a 20 µL loop and separated, at ambient temperature. Data handling system comprised of an IBM personal computer and P/ACE system MDQ software.

The column used for separation was µ-Bondapak C18 (300 × 3.9 mm, 10 µm i.d.). The mobile phase consisting of a mixture of methanol and deionized water in the

ratio 78 : 22 v/v was delivered at a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min. The mobile phase was filtered through a 0.45 μ nylon filter and sonicated for 15 min. Analysis was performed at ambient temperature. Before sample injection, the column was conditioned with mobile phase for 20 min.

Results and discussion

Drug quality control, stability, metabolism, pharmacokinetics and toxicity studies necessitate the determination of drugs in pharmaceutical formulations and biological samples. Correspondingly, efficient and validated analytical methods are very critical requirements for all these investigations. HPLC is the most widely used technique for this purpose.

Optimization of the chromatographic conditions :

The aim of the present study was to develop a simple isocratic, accurate and sensitive HPLC method for the simultaneous determination of EZE and SIM in their fixed dose combination. Initially various mobile phases and stationary phases were tested to obtain the best separation and resolution between EZE and SIM. The mobile phase consisting of methanol : water (78 : 22 v/v) was found appropriate for separation of both the components using Waters Corporation μ -Bondapack C₁₈ column. The chromatographic conditions were optimized to get best resolution between the two analytes. The mobile phase composition was varied from 65 : 35 (v/v) methanol/

water to 95 : 5 (v/v) methanol/water in order to assess the impact of the methanol content on the separation and chromatographic parameters like resolution, tailing factor and number of theoretical plates. The addition of methanol as a less polar solvent than water will reduce the retention time of the analyte due to reduction of surface tension of water. Although increase of methanol contents to 95% reduced the retention time of SIM to 6.3 min, the retention time of EZE increased to 5.7 min and resolution between EZE and SIM decreased to 0.53 indicating overlap between the two drugs. So, by applying the optimum chromatographic conditions, resolved sharp peaks that belong to EZE and SIM were obtained at retention times of 4.4 and 8.3 min respectively (Fig. 2).

To select the optimum flow rate of mobile phase, different flow rates in the range 0.6–1.1 mL/min were investigated. 0.8 ml/min was chosen as it gave good resolution in a suitable time. On increasing the flow rate to 1.1 ml/min, the retention time increased to 5.8 and 11.9 min for EZE and SIM, respectively. This is due to decrease in column efficiency and increase in plate height by increasing flow rate.

To select the absorption wavelength for detection, UV spectra of EZE and SIM were acquired and overlaid. It was found that the best response for the two drugs was obtained at 238 nm (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Typical chromatogram of simvastatin and ezetimibe.

Fig. 3. UV-Spectra of (a) ezetimibe 50 µg/mL and (b) simvastatin 50 µg/mL in methanol : water (78 : 22 v/v).

From the above investigation, it was found that the optimum conditions for separation of EZE and SIM were μ -Bondapak C₁₈, 3.9 × 300 mm, 10 µm i.d. column with a simple mobile phase consisted of methanol : water (78 : 22 v/v), delivered at a flow rate of 0.8 mL min⁻¹ and wavelength of detection at 238 nm.

Method validation :

The developed chromatographic method for the simultaneous determination of EZE and SIM was validated using ICH guidelines^{18,19}. Assessed validation parameters include system suitability, linearity, limits of detection and quantification, accuracy, precision and robustness.

System suitability : In order to determine the adequate resolution and reproducibility of the proposed methodology, suitability parameters including retention time, resolution, tailing factor, capacity factor, selectivity factor, % RSD of retention times and peak areas were investigated. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Selectivity : Chromatographic methods are selective if excipients do not interfere with the analysis. To identify the interference by excipients, a mixture of inactive ingredients (placebo), standard solutions, and the commercial pharmaceutical preparations including EZE and SIM were analyzed by the developed method. The representative chromatogram (Fig. 4) did not show any other peaks for excipients, which confirmed the selectivity of the method.

Table 1. System suitability data

Parameter	Results		Acceptance criteria
	EZE	SIM	
Retention time (min)	4.4	8.3	-
Capacity factor (k')	0.83	2.23	1-10
Selectivity factor (α)		2.7	> 1.0
Resolution factor (R_s)		5.06	> 2.0
Tailing factor	1.38	1.50	NMT 2.0
% RSD of peak area	0.65	0.56	NMT 2.0%
% RSD of retention time	0.62	0.48	NMT 2.0%

Linearity : The linearity of an analytical procedure is its ability (within a given range) to obtain test results which are directly proportional to the concentration (amount) of analyte in the sample. Linearity of detector response for EZE/SIM was established by analyzing serial dilutions of a stock solution of the working standard. Six concentrations over the range cited in Table 2 were prepared and analyzed. The final concentration of each solution in µg per ml was plotted against peak area response. Results from linear regression analysis of response and concentration data are given in Table 2. The correlation coefficient from the linear regression analysis was calculated and found to be greater than 0.9999 in case of both analytes. This indicates that there exists a good linear relationship between concentration of drugs and the peak area.

Fig. 4. Chromatograms of ezetimibe and simvastatin tablets (1 : 1 w/w EZE/SIM).

Table 2. Analytical performance data for the determination of ezetimibe and simvastatin using the proposed method

Parameter	Ezetimibe	Simvastatin
Concentration range ($\mu\text{mg/mL}$)	0.5–50.0	0.6–60.0
Intercept (<i>a</i>)	10.68	3.90
Slope (<i>b</i>)	55.58	71.10
Correlation coefficient [®]	0.9999	0.9999
Retention time (min)	4.4	8.3
$S_{y/x}$ (Residual standard deviation)	5.82	12.92
S_a (Standard deviation of intercept)	0.54	0.54
S_b (Standard deviation of slope)	0.14	0.26
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.50	0.60
LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.25	0.26

Limit of detection and limit of quantification : LOD and LOQ were determined according to the ICH^{18,19} guidelines, LOD was determined by establishing the minimum level of which the analyte can reliably be detected, LOQ is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be determined with acceptable precision and accuracy under the stated experimental conditions. The results are illustrated in Table 2.

Accuracy and precision : The accuracy of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between the value which is accepted either as a conventional true value or an accepted reference value and the value found. To prove the accuracy of the proposed method, the % recovery and % error were determined over the working concentration ranges for both drugs cited in Table 2. The results are shown in Table 3.

Intraday and interday precisions were assessed using three concentrations and three replicates of each concentration for both drugs. The relative standard deviations were found to be less than 2.0 indicating reasonable, repeatability and intermediate precision of the proposed method (Table 3).

Table 3. Accuracy and precision data for ezetimibe and simvastatin using the proposed method

Analyte	Actual concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Experimental concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)	Error (%)	
Intraday ^a	SIM	11.36	11.54 \pm 0.25	101.50	0.33	1.56
	SIM	18.40	18.46 \pm 0.15	100.32	0.28	0.32
	SIM	56.80	56.84 \pm 1.00	100.08	0.50	0.07
EZE	EZE	9.68	9.57 \pm 0.04	98.95	0.10	0.10
	EZE	11.84	11.88 \pm 0.09	100.33	0.66	0.33
	EZE	48.10	48.42 \pm 0.55	100.04	0.74	0.84
Interday ^b	SIM	11.36	11.48 \pm 0.09	101.30	0.42	1.29
	SIM	18.40	18.44 \pm 0.45	100.26	0.27	0.21
	SIM	56.80	56.07 \pm 0.57	98.71	1.91	1.30
EZE	EZE	9.68	9.57 \pm 0.81	98.85	0.25	1.10
	EZE	11.84	11.89 \pm 0.15	100.35	0.59	0.42
	EZE	48.40	47.75 \pm 0.42	98.67	1.25	1.34

^aMean \pm SD for *n* = 3. ^bMean \pm SD for *n* = 3.

Robustness : Robustness of the method was checked by making slight deliberate changes in chromatographic conditions like mobile phase ratio, flow rate and wavelength. It was observed that there were no marked changes in chromatograms which demonstrated that the developed RP-HPLC method is robust.

Table 4. Application of the proposed method to the analysis of ezetimibe and simvastatin in LIPITIN® tablets

Ratio EZE/SIM	Label claim (mg) EZE/SIM	% Label claim estimated EZE	Mean % ^a	% Label claim estimated SIM	Mean (%) ^a
1 : 1	10 : 10	99.75	100.21	100.59	101.30
		99.80		101.12	
		101.08		102.20	
1 : 2	10 : 20	100.20	100.60	98.47	98.92
		100.90		99.08	
		100.47		99.19	
1 : 4	10 : 40	99.01	99.18	98.78	98.6
		99.66		98.91	
		98.87		98.20	

^aThe percentage of relative standard deviation %RSD ≤ 2.0%.

Application to synthetic mixtures and tablet formulations :

To prove the validity and the applicability of the proposed method, four synthetic mixtures of different ratios (1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 4 and 1 : 8 EZE : SIM) were assayed. The results obtained were precise and accurate over the different proportions of drug components analyzed by the proposed method. The percentage recoveries were 98.90–101.60 and 98.92–101.60 for EZE and SIM, respectively.

The applicability of the proposed method was examined by analyzing commercial LIPITRIN® tablets. The obtained results of the test solution are shown in Table 4. All the obtained data fully met the criteria from the ICH regulative in every observed segment of the method validation.

Conclusion :

A new RP-HPLC method with UV detection is proposed for simultaneous analysis of EZE and SIM. The proposed method is considered as the best simple method proven to be capable to rapid simultaneous separation and quantitative determination of EZE and SIM using a very simple mobile phase which does not include buffers. This method has provided good sensitivity and excellent reproducibility with a run less than 10 min for its combined drugs determination. The method is accurate and precise for reliable quality control evaluation of drugs with good accuracy and precision. From these values it is concluded that the new RP-HPLC method is suitable for the simultaneous determination of these two components in their pharmaceutical formulations.

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References

1. P. Patil, V. Patil and A. Paradkar, *Acta Pharm.*, 2007, **57**, 111.
2. <http://www.netdoctor.co.uk/medicines/100005103.html>.
3. R. P. Dixit, C. R. Barhate, S. G. Padhye, C. L. Viswanathan and M. S. Nagarsenker, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2010, **72**, 204.
4. J. R. Sama, R. R. Kalakuntla, R. V. S. Narayana and P. Reddanna, *J. Pharm. Soc.*, 2010, **2**, 82.
5. P. Nagaraju and V. Z. Vishnu, *J. Glob. Pharm. Tech.*, 2009, **2**, 113.
6. D. A. Kumar, D. P. Sujana, V. Vijayasree and J. V. L. Rao, *E-J. Chem.*, 2009, **6**, 541.
7. M. Ashfaq, I. U. Khan, S. S. Qutab and S. N. Razzaq, *J. Chil. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **52**, 1220.
8. M. Hefnawy, M. Al-Omar and S. Julkhuf, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2009, **50**, 527.
9. B. G. Chaudhari, N. M. Patel and P. B. Shah, *J. AOAC Int.*, 2007, **90**, 1242.
10. R. P. Dixi, C. R. Barhate and M. S. Nagarsenker, *Chromatogr.*, 2008, **67**, 101.
11. C. Yardimci and N. Ozaltin, *J. Chromatogr. Sci.*, 2010, **48**, 95.
12. M. K. Srinivasu, R. A. Narasa and R. G. Om, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2002, **29**, 715.
13. M. Farouk, O. Abdel-Aziz, R. Nagi and L. M. Abdel-Fattah, *J. Biomed. Sci. Res.*, 2010, **2**, 202.

14. S. Balaji and A. Sunitha, *Pak. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2010, **23**, 375.
15. H. M. Maher, R. M. Youssef, E. M. Hassan, M. A. El-Kimary and E. I. Barary, *Drug Test Anal.*, 2010, in press.
16. I. M. Palabiyik, F. Onur, C. Yardimci and N. Ozaltin, *Quim. Nova.*, 2008, **31**, 1121.
17. S. J. Rajput and H. A. Raj, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2007, **69**, 759.
18. ICH (Q₂A), Note for guidance on validation of analytical methods definition and terminology. International Conference on Harmonisation, IFPMA, Geneva, 1994.
19. ICH (Q₂B), Note for guidance on validation of analytical procedures, methodology. International Conference on Harmonisation, IFPMA, Geneva, 1994.

